

Naphtho(2,3-*d*)pyrimido(2,1-*b*)(1,3)thiazines

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Some Naphtho(2,3-*d*)pyrimido(2,1-*b*)(1,3)thiazine derivatives have been synthesised by the condensation of 3-amino 2-naphthoic acid with β -isothiocyanoketones and finally cyclisation with PPA. The structure has been confirmed by analysis and i.r. studies and by comparing one of them with its isomeric benzo(*g*)(1,3)thiazino(2,3-*b*)quinazoline derivative prepared by an unambiguous route involving the condensation of 3-amino 2-naphthoic acid with 2-mercapto 4, 4, 6 trimethyl 4*H*, (1,3)thiazine.

In our attempts to evolve new systems with probable biological activity around the general pattern of already known drugs, some naphtho(2,3-*d*)pyrimido(2,1-*b*)(1,3)thiazines have been synthesised by the condensation of 3-amino 2-naphthoic acid with β -isothiocyanoketones.

Isothiocyanates are known to react with amines more readily than ketones. So the first step would lead to the formation of thiourea derivative which could cyclise in two ways to give rise to IVa or Va through the formation of IV or V respectively. Contrary to our previous observations^{1,2,3} where the condensation always led to the formation of the final product, in the present case the intermediate IV has been isolated. This structure, besides analytical results has been confirmed by absence of i.r. absorption band at 1650 cm^{-1} for C=O present originally in 3-amino 2-naphthoic acid. The band at 3460 cm^{-1} for -OH of COOH group also disappears. Instead two new i.r. absorption bands at

1694 cm^{-1} due to $\text{R}'''-\text{C}(=\text{O})-\text{CH}_2$ and 1670 cm^{-1}

due to $\text{C}(\text{S})=\text{O}$ appear. Moreover this intermediate

IV on cyclisation with PPA gives rise to IVa. The structure of IVa has been confirmed by elemental analysis and by preparing the alternative structure Va by an unambiguous route involving the condensation of 3-amino 2-naphthoic acid with 2-mercapto 4,4,6 trimethyl 4*H*(1,3)thiazine.

It has been found that the product obtained by the former route differs from the product obtained by latter condensation in i.r., m.p., m.m.p. and tlc; thus the product obtained by the condensation of 3-amino 2-naphthoic acid and β -isothiocyanoketones and finally cyclisation with PPA may be assigned structure IV.

Further this structure finds support from earlier observations from these laboratories.^{1,2,3}

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open glass capillaries in liquid paraffin bath and are uncorrected; i.r. spectra were taken in nujol on Perkin-Elmer grating i.r. spectrophotometer-621.

Condensation of 3-amino 2-naphthoic acid with 2-methyl 2-isothiocyanopentanone-4, i.e., Isolation of 2-[(1,1-Dimethyl-3-Oxobutyl)-imino]-1,2-dihydro 4*H*-naphtho(2,3-*d*)(1-3)thiazin-4-one IV ($\text{R}' = \text{R}'' = \text{R}''' = \text{CH}_3$):

A mixture of 3-amino 2-naphthoic acid (1.87 g, 0.01 mol) and 2-methyl 2-isothiocyanopentanone-4 (1.57 g, 0.01 mol) was heated on an oil bath at 115-120° for 4 hours, when it changed to a hard mass.

TABLE—NAPHTHO-PYRIMIDO-THIAZINES AND THEIR INTERMEDIATES

Compound No.	R'	R''	R'''	m.p. °C	Yield %	MF	Analytical results	
							Found %	Calculated %
IV	CH ₃	CH ₃	CH ₃	213	78	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂ S	C, 66.17 H, 6.00 N, 8.97	66.25 5.52 8.59
IVa	"	"	"	345	62	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₂ OS	C, 70.00 H, 5.61 N, 8.82	70.13 5.20 9.09
IV	"	"	C ₂ H ₅	215	71	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂ S	C, 66.89 H, 6.07 N, 8.43	67.07 5.88 8.69
IVa	"	"	"	>340	56	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₂ OS	C, 67.43 H, 6.51 N, 8.30	67.80 6.21 7.91
IV	"	C ₂ H ₅	"	224	66	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	N, 8.02	8.33
IVa	"	"	"	>340	54	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₂ OS		

All compounds were crystallised from ethanol.

After cooling, the product was washed with a little ether and finally with water. Crystallisation from ethanol gave white needles.

2-methyl 2-isothiocyanohexanone-4 and 3-methyl 3-isothiocyanooheptanone-5 were also condensed with 3-amino-2-naphthoic acid in a similar way. The data regarding the yields of these compounds, solvent for crystallisation, m.p. and analytical results are tabulated.

1,3,3 trialkyl 3H, 6H naphtho(2,3-*d*) pyrimido(2,1-*b*)(1,3) thiazin-6-one(IVa) :

The intermediate IV(1.5 g) was mixed with PPA (prepared from 3 ml of orthophosphoric acid and 4.0 g of P₂O₅) and the contents heated on an oil bath at 140-50° for 3 hours. After cooling and diluting it with ice cold water (40 ml), the contents were basified with 5% sodium carbonate solution and collected under suction. The product was finally washed with water and crystallised. The product V(R'=R''=R'''=CH₃) gives an i.r. absorp-

tion band at 1670 cm⁻¹ for

The data regarding the yields of these compounds, their m.p., solvent for crystallisation and analytical results are tabulated.

Condensation of 3-amino 2-naphthoic acid with 2-mercapto 4 : 4 : 6 trimethyl 4H(1,3), thiazine, i.e., synthesis of 2,4,4, trimethyl 4H, 6H-benzo(g)(1,3) thiazino(2, 3-*b*)-quinazolin-6-one(Va) (R'=R''=R'''=CH₃) :

A mixture of 3-amino 2-naphthoic acid hydrochloride (2.24 g, 0.01 mol) and 2-mercapto 4,4,6

trimethyl 4H(1,3) thiazine (1.73 g, 0.01 mol) was heated on an oil bath to 130° when there was evolution of H₂S. The temperature was raised to 150-155° and the contents heated at this temperature for 4 hours when the evolution of H₂S practically ceased. After cooling, the product was triturated with a little of ethanol and filtered. Crystallisation from ethanol gave brownish product m.p. 330°, yield being 1.6 g (52%). It gives an i.r. absorp-

tion band at 1678 cm⁻¹ for . Found C, 69.83 ; H, 5.02 C₁₈H₁₆N₂OS requires C, 70.1%, H, 5.20%.

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